

Exploring the full magneto-ionic oxidation spectrum in Pt/CoFeB/HfO₂

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We show that in Pt/CoFeB/HfO₂ a wide range of oxidation levels at the ferromagnet/oxide interface can be accessed through magneto-ionic gating using ionic-liquid gates. Perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA) is induced at intermediate oxidation levels, while two in-plane anisotropy states with non-equivalent ionic states are induced for under-oxidised and over-oxidised interfaces. This system shows reversibility and non-volatility in the whole range of oxidation states, where oxidation levels have been monitored by X-ray absorption spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. This study shows that multistate magneto-ionic memory elements with a wider range of intermediate states can be designed by leveraging both under- and over-oxidation around the optimal oxidation state that induces PMA.

Magneto-ionic materials constitute a solid platform for the design of devices where non-volatile and analogue gate control of magnetic properties can be achieved through voltage-driven ionic motion. Their design has greatly advanced in recent years, in particular concerning the diversity of the mobile species driven by gate voltages which include oxygen-based ions¹⁻⁵, H⁺^{6,7} Li⁺⁸ and N-based ions^{9,10}. One of the main applications perspectives of magneto-ionic devices is their use as multi-state memory elements with both ionic and magnetic degrees of freedom^{11,12}. It is therefore important to design devices and materials that could offer a wide range of intermediate magneto-ionic states.

One rather unexplored opportunity in magneto-ionics is the use of the full spectrum of oxidation states in oxygen driven magneto-ionic materials. It is known that the optimum degree of oxidation at the ferromagnetic/oxide interface in ferromagnetic ultra-thin films favours perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA), and that either over/under-oxidation leads to its weakening and subsequent loss driving the system into an in-plane magnetic anisotropy (IPA) state¹³. In this context, a magneto-ionic system that could map the entire oxidation spectrum between under- and over-oxidation can provide not only a continuum of states between IPA and PMA, but also intermediate states having equivalent anisotropies but different ionic states, introducing new functionalities.

It has been shown that a high degree of complexity of the magneto-ionic mechanism is at play when the full range of oxidation is considered. Two regimes with different dynamics have been identified, one where magneto ionic gating drives

IPA in the under-oxidised state to PMA (regime I), and one where PMA goes into IPA due to over-oxidation (regime II). In Ta/CoFeB/HfO₂ it was shown that the transition IPA → PMA in the under-oxidation regime occurs at a faster rate than the transition PMA → IPA in the over-oxidation regime, and that these transitions are irreversible and reversible, respectively, for the same applied gate voltages¹. Studies in the literature explore the IPA to PMA transition, and vice versa, in either regimes I or II^{3,5,14-16}. However, few studies show the full transition IPA → PMA → IPA, where either high operation temperatures were used¹⁷ or where the system shows limited retention⁴.

In this study, ionic liquid gating was used to explore the full range of oxidation in Pt/CoFeB/HfO₂ layers where reversibility and non-volatility are obtained throughout. The full IPA → PMA → IPA transition is observed due to the progressive oxidation of Fe and Co atoms under the action of a negative gate voltage, which was confirmed by the analysis of X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements before and after gating. The oxidation is accompanied by a loss in magnetic moment as well as a reduction in the magnitude of the interfacial Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction in the system, which is proposed to be linked to ion intercalation at the Pt/CoFeB interface. These results bring important insights for the design of materials and devices with magneto-ionic functionalities.

The magnetic stacks used in this study were grown at room temperature using a Singulus Rotaris deposition system, the films were then used as-deposited. Metals (Pt (5 nm), Co₆₀Fe₂₀B₂₀ (0.7 nm)) were DC-sputtered and HfO₂ (2 nm) was RF-sputtered. The ionic liquid gate was composed of ionic liquid (IL)

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FIG. 1. (a) Graphic representation of the magneto-ionic gating device and the chemical structure of the ionic liquid. (b),(c) Evolution of the magnetic anisotropy under negative gate voltages measured by anomalous Hall effect, the colour scale bar illustrates the gate-induced changes in magnetic anisotropy. (d) and (e) Time evolution of the final magnetic states obtained in (b) and (c), respectively.

[EMI]⁺[TFSI]⁻ (cation: 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium, anion: bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide), which was added to the surface of the film. A glass substrate coated with a 100 nm thick indium tin oxide (ITO) layer was used as a counter electrode to apply the gate voltages, Figure 1 (a) shows the schematic of the device and the chemical structure of the ionic liquid¹⁸. The gate voltages informed in this study are applied always to the ITO counter electrode. All the magnetic films studied have in-plane magnetic anisotropy in the as-grown state. Fig. 1 (b) shows anomalous Hall effect (AHE) hysteresis loops under gate voltages of increasing amplitude going from -2 V to -2.3 V where, as the gate voltage increases, the system transitions from the as-grown state with a dominant IPA into a dominant PMA state after the application of -2.3 V for 300 s. Figure 1 (c) shows a similar

experiment where the as-grown state was driven in one step into a dominant PMA state with a gate voltage application of -2.3 V for 300 s, and subsequently subject to a gate voltage of -2.4 V, which drives the system into dominant IPA state (the full gating sequence and additional hysteresis loops are available in the supplementary information). The final magnetic state obtained in these two experiments was monitored over 60 days, as shown in Fig. 1 (d) and (e), where only minor changes were observed, confirming the non-volatility of the magneto-ionic effects.

The cartoon above each plot in Fig. 1 (b) and (c) uses a colour scale to indicate the full anisotropy transition accessible under negative gate voltages, starting from the initial as-grown state with IPA, over the PMA state, and ending in another IPA state. As this transition happens under negative gate voltages, it is expected that oxygen-based negatively charged ionic species, such as OH⁻ ions, would migrate towards the CoFeB/HfO₂ interface and oxidise the Fe and Co atoms, producing the observed effects in anisotropy. It is therefore likely that the two IPA anisotropy states observed at either side of the PMA state correspond to two distinct chemical states with different oxidation levels of the CoFeB/HfO₂ interface. Taking the PMA state as a reference point, the two IPA anisotropy states located left and right in the cartoon presented in Fig. 1 (b) and (c) correspond to a CoFeB/HfO₂ interface that is under-oxidised, and over-oxidised, respectively. This is in line with previous works showing the link between interface oxidation and magnetic anisotropy in ultra-thin films^{13,19}.

The hypothesis of an oxidation-driven magneto-ionic mechanism was confirmed by X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) measurements, which were performed on an as-grown sample, as well as on the two samples obtained after a final gating step of -2.3 V for 300 s, and -2.4 V for 360 s presented in Fig. 1. XAS measurements were conducted after the time evolution measurements were concluded. Fig. 2 shows the full XAS spectra at the L₂ and L₃ edges of Co (a) and Fe (b). The L₃ profile in the as-grown sample shows a main peak centered around 710.8 eV for Fe and 781.8 eV for Co, which closely resembles the profile obtained for reference samples of metallic Fe and Co (see supplementary information) and similar experiments in the literature^{2,19}. This indicates that the as-grown state of the samples contains a relatively low content of Fe and Co oxides, supporting the idea that the IPA anisotropy observed is linked to an oxygen deficiency at the CoFeB/HfO₂ interface. The exposure of the as-grown samples to gate voltages of -2.3 V for 300 s and -2.4 V for 360 s induces the progressive appearance of a shoulder at higher energies, centered at approximately 783.2 eV, in the Co L₃ edge profile. A more visible contribution from a higher energy component of the absorption is observed in the Fe L₃ edge profile, where a prominent peak centered at approximately 712.3 eV appears and dominates the intensity over that of the initial peak observed in the as-grown sample. The appearance of features at high absorption energies is a signature of a change in chemical environment compatible with oxidation of the Fe and Co atoms. It is likely that the more pronounced effects observed in the Fe edge are due to the fact that Fe oxidises at a faster rate compared to Co²⁰

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FIG. 2. (a),(b) Full XAS spectra at the Co and Fe edges for as-grown and gated samples. (c) Fitting of the L_3 edge of Co and Fe. The inset in (a) shows the percentage of the as-grown component present in gated samples, as extracted from the fittings in (c).

but also to the fact that the concentration of Fe is three times lower than that of Co, therefore, the oxidation effect could lead to a more pronounced impact on the total Fe content. In order to gain more insight into the oxidation of Fe and Co, the L_3 edge profile was modeled as a combination of Gaussian curves as presented in Fig. 2 (c). As the L_2 edge does not present a structure with well defined features as the one of the L_3 edge, it has not been considered in the analysis. Initially, the L_3 edge profile of the as-grown sample was

modeled including three Gaussian curves for both Fe and Co, this allowed to use the modeled profile of the edge as a fitting parameter for the L_3 edge profiles of the gated samples, as shown in the central and bottom panels in Fig. 2 (c). For both Fe and Co, the contribution of the as-grown sample decreases as a function of gating, while the other two components, modeled as two additional Gaussian curves, give rise to the spectral features appearing at higher absorption energies. The reduction of the as-grown contribution as a function of gating, and therefore oxidation, has been plotted in the inset of Fig. 2 (b) for both Fe and Co. As mentioned earlier, the gate-induced reduction of the as-grown contribution is more prominent in Fe than in Co, which can drop to nearly 50% in Fe, compared to a drop to about 70% for Co. As mentioned, this can be due to the fact that oxidation occurs at a faster rate in Fe compared to Co²⁰. This does not only confirm that the changes observed in magnetic anisotropy are related to oxidation of both Fe and Co, but also that a change in composition within the ferromagnetic phase could take place after gating, as the Fe and Co contents do not decrease by the same amount.

As this system shows a wide range of oxidation-driven magneto-ionic states it is important to evaluate the reversibility of the magneto-ionic process. Fig. 3 (a) shows the anomalous Hall effect hysteresis loops of an as-grown sample and after the application of a gate voltage of -2.1 V for 100 s, which induces the appearance of a dominant PMA component of the anisotropy. The same gating protocol is applied to a third sample, adding a gate application of +3.3 V for 300 s to reverse the magnetic state to the initial IPA in the under-oxidised state. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements for binding energies corresponding to Co and Fe $2p$ edges were performed in these three samples and are presented in Fig. 3 (b) and (c), respectively. These samples contained a capping layer of 1.5 nm of HfO_2 , instead of the 2 nm used in all other experiments presented in this work, to maximise the intensity of the signal collected from the buried Co and Fe atoms. The XPS signal from Co shows that the intensity of the peak centered around 778.2 eV, corresponding to the Co $2p_{3/2}$ levels, decreases significantly after applying a gate voltage of -2.1 V for 100 s. This is accompanied by the appearance of a prominent feature centered around 780.1 eV, which corresponds to the binding energies of electrons in the Co $2p_{3/2}$ levels in CoO_x , a behaviour that has also been reported in other studies^{16,21}. The subsequent application of +3.3 V for 300 s results in the opposite effect, the Co metallic peak intensity significantly recovers, while the feature at higher binding energies loses intensity. A similar behaviour is observed for the Co $2p_{1/2}$ levels located between 790 eV and 800 eV.

While the signal from Co can be analysed in terms of a variation in the degree of oxidation of Co, the signal from Fe presented in Fig. 3 (c) shows a significantly reduced amplitude and a profile dominated by a feature between 710 eV and 715 eV, that can be linked to the Fe $2p_{3/2}$ levels in Fe_2O_3 . The feature appearing between 700 eV and 705 eV, appearing after the first gating cycle, can be associated to the $2p_{3/2}$ levels of In, which may appear due to the diffusion of

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FIG. 3. (a) Hysteresis loops for the three samples studied. XPS spectra for (b) Fe and (c) Co for samples as-grown, and after gating under -2.1V for 100s, and subsequent +3.3V for 300s.

In atoms coming from the ITO counter electrode through the ionic liquid. As mentioned earlier, the relatively low signal of the Fe levels can be due to the fact that the concentration of Fe is three times lower than that of Co. Nevertheless, a feature centered at around 707 eV (see dotted line in Fig. 3 (c)) is seen to decrease and increase in intensity as negative and positive voltages are applied, respectively. This feature can be associated to the Fe $2p_{3/2}$ levels in metallic Fe, which also points to a gate-driven change in oxidation state of Fe in this system. The dominant oxidation signal seen in the XPS signal of Fe in the as-grown sample contrasts with the XAS signal, which shows negligible signs of oxidation. This could be due to the fact that this sample contains a thinner capping layer of 1.5 nm, which could make it more susceptible to oxidation in the as-grown state. However, XPS as conducted in this study has a probing depth that is significantly lower than the high-flux XAS measurements conducted at the synchrotron. This results in a reduced probing depth in XPS with respect to XAS, in addition to the attenuation of the Fe and Co signal produced by the presence of a capping HfO₂ layer. This can lead to XPS being more sensitive to the upper-most atomic layers of the CoFeB, compared to the bulk sensitivity provided by XAS. Therefore, the XPS measurements presented here could be significantly more sensitive to the CoFeB/HfO₂ interface atoms with respect to XAS. A similar scenario between the XPS and XAS measurements has been previously reported for the gating effects on Pt/Co/HfO₂¹⁶. It is therefore concluded that a significant part of the interfacial Fe present in the system is oxidised before gating occurs, while Co shows a dominant metallic state. These measurements show that the reversibility observed between the IPA underoxidised state and the PMA state, induced through gate-driven oxidation, is related to the recovery of the metallic state under positive voltage, and may be extended to the full range of gate-induced oxidation states that go beyond PMA and into the over-oxidised regime. Fig. 4 (a) shows AHE hysteresis loops within a full magneto-

FIG. 4. (a) Hysteresis loops across a full magneto-ionic cycle under gate voltages of -2V, +2V, +3V and +3.3V, the gate-induced changes in magnetic anisotropy are depicted in (b). (c) Amplitude of the anomalous Hall effect signal at 0.8 mT (dotted line in (a)) as a function of time through one magneto-ionic cycle under gate voltages of -2V and +3.3V, and (d) ten consecutive cycles. (e) Time evolution measurements for two magneto-ionic states achieved through the application of positive gate voltages.

ionic cycle, showing reversibility over the entire span of accessible magneto-ionic states. Starting from an underoxidised IPA state the system goes through PMA to reach an IPA overoxidised state under a gate voltage of -2V, the process is reversed under gate voltages of +2V, +3V and +3.3V. The gate-induced reversible changes in magnetic anisotropy for negative and positive gate voltages are summarised in the cartoon presented in Fig. 4 (b). Fig. 4 (c) shows a continuous measurement of the AHE voltage as a function of time for a single magneto-ionic cycle conducted under gate voltages of -2V and +3.3V. A peak in the AHE voltage is observed for both negative and positive gate voltage applications, corresponding to the PMA state. Ten repetitions of this full magneto-ionic cycle are presented in Fig. 4 (d), demonstrating the cyclability of the magneto-ionic process. These measurements are performed under a constant magnetic field of 0.8 mT to avoid a loss of signal due to the formation of a multidomain state when transitioning from IPA to PMA. The AHE voltage signal variation accounts for the changes in magnetic anisotropy, but also contains a component of a gate-dependent offset responsible for the large negative

amplitude observed in the IPA state (overoxidised) achieved at the end of the application of -2 V and the mismatch between the AHE voltage amplitudes at the beginning and at the end of the cycle (see supplementary information). The discrepancies with the dynamics presented in Fig. 1 under a gate voltage of -2 V are due to the evolution of the magneto-ionic dynamics over the course of several cycles, the hysteresis loops presented in Fig. 4 (a) correspond to a third cycle, which is more representative of the dynamics that follow in the subsequent cycles presented in (c) and (d), compared to the first cycle done starting from the as-grown material, as shown in Fig. 1. A more extensive description of this feature and further cycling measurements can be found in the supplementary information.

Fig. 4 (e) shows (left) the time evolution of a PMA state recovered from an IPA overoxidised state (previously set using negative gate voltages) under the application of positive gate voltages, and (right) a state where the PMA state was significantly quenched (within the underoxidised regime) through further exposure to a positive gate voltage (see supplementary information for the full gating sequence). The time evolution after application of a positive gate voltage, unlike the samples subject to oxidation (negative voltages), shows a significant decrease in coercivity over time for the two magneto-ionic states presented in the left and right panels of Fig. 4 (e). However, a dominant perpendicular magnetic anisotropy and a strong quenching of the PMA are retained for each of these two magneto-ionic states, respectively. A strong time evolution of magneto-ionic states set by a gate-induced reduction process has been observed in the literature, as well as the relatively more stable nature of the states generated by an oxidation process, which has been associated to a spontaneous re-oxidation after the gate voltage is switched off^{4,12,15}. While reported changes in the remanence indicate an evolution of the magnetic anisotropy over time after positive gate voltage application (reduction)^{12,15}, in the present case, the coercivity change is not accompanied by a significant change in the saturation-to-remnance ratio. This shows that despite the variations observed in the coercivity, which can be heavily influenced by extrinsic parameters such as disorder, there is a relatively good retention of the magneto-ionic states obtained after reduction under positive gate voltages.

The impact of magneto-ionic gating on the Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (DMI) in this system has also been evaluated. Brillouin light scattering (BLS) measurements were conducted in as-grown samples, as well as in the same gated samples presented earlier (samples from Figs. 1 and 2), obtained after the final application of gate voltages of -2.3 V for 300 s and -2.4 V for 360 s. The presence of DMI gives rise to a non-reciprocity of the propagation of spin-waves in the system, which manifests itself as a frequency shift between the inelastic scattering Stokes and anti-Stokes peaks of the BLS spectrum^{22,23}. This frequency shift (ΔF) is plotted as a function of the spin-wave vector k_{sw} , for the three samples described previously, in Fig. 5 (a), (BLS spectra and fittings can be found in the supplementary information). The slope of these curves is equal to $2\gamma D/\pi M_s$, where γ is the

FIG. 5. (a) Frequency shift between the inelastic scattering Stokes and anti-Stokes peaks of the BLS spectrum (ΔF) as a function of the spin-wave vector k_{sw} . (b) $M_s \cdot t$ and D_s for the as-grown and gated samples (-2.3 V for 300 s and -2.4 V for 360 s).

gyromagnetic ratio, D is the DMI effective constant and M_s is the saturation magnetisation. In order to extract the values of D , vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM) measurements were conducted to determine M_s and are presented in Fig. 5 (b) (VSM hysteresis loops can be found in the supplementary information). In the pristine sample, considering the nominal CoFeB thickness of 0.7 nm , $M_s = 1.54 \times 10^6\text{ A/m}$ and $D = -2.1\text{ mJ/m}^2$. However, in ultra-thin films, the thickness of the magnetic layer t can significantly diverge from the nominal value due to the formation of magnetically dead layers at the CoFeB interfaces^{24,25}. This is particularly relevant in magneto-ionic systems, where oxidation and reduction processes are induced through gating and can significantly change the thickness of an ultra-thin magnetic film which is typically of a few atomic layers. Therefore, in the present case the values informed for the as-grown and gated samples are $D_s = D \cdot t$ and $M_s \cdot t$, and are presented in Fig. 5 (b).

It has been shown that the contribution of oxides to the DMI can be significant and that in the case of Pt/CoFe/MgO, oxidation can result in the overall increase in D ²⁶. However, in the present case the oxidation of the Fe and Co under negative gate voltages leads to a decrease in the magnetic moment and also to a reduction in the absolute value of D_s . As mentioned earlier, the oxidation of Co and Fe at the CoFeB/HfO₂ interface is crucial for defining magnetic anisotropy, however, in terms of the DMI, the largest contribution in this system is seeded at the Pt/CoFeB interface. A similar scenario was observed in Pt/Co/HfO₂¹⁶ and the gate-induced change in DMI was attributed to ion intercalation, as the reduction of DMI is linked to a decoupling between the Pt and CoFeB layers. Although gate-induced oxidation at the Pt/CoFeB interface can not be ruled out, a gate-induced intercalation of ions and reordering of the interfacial structure are likely to play a dominant role in modulating the DMI. It is interesting to observe that the monotonic decrease over the three data points measured corresponds to three different magneto-ionic states, IPA in the under-oxidised regime, PMA, and IPA in the over-oxidised regime, which shows that the effects on anisotropy are not necessarily correlated to the effects on D_s , which shows a monotonic decrease in amplitude as a function of oxidation. However, an accurate measurement of t would be needed to further conclude about the correlation between

PMA and DMI in magneto-ionic experiments. In conclusion, we show that a wide range of magneto-ionic states can be obtained by exploiting the full oxidation spectrum going from under-oxidation to over-oxidation, relative to the oxidation content that gives rise to PMA. The oxidative mechanism in Pt/CoFeB/HfO₂ has been confirmed by XAS measurements, a signature of higher oxidation states and a reduction of the content of metallic Co and Fe have been observed as a function of the application of a negative gate voltage by means of ionic liquid gating. The magnetic states achieved through the application of negative gate voltages are reversible under a positive gate voltage and exhibit a relatively good retention. The reversibility mechanism was identified as a reduction process by XPS. The gate-induced oxidation also entails a progressive reduction in the magnetic moment and a reduction of the absolute value of D_s . These results show that magneto-ionic devices allow to reversibly access a wide variety of intermediate states over two transitions from IPA to PMA by exploiting the available diversity in oxidation states. These results bring interesting perspectives for the design of magneto-ionic devices for multi-state memories and synaptic elements.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The supplementary information contains additional measurements and information about XAS, XPS and BLS experiments, the full gating sequence of all the samples presented and additional AHE reversibility measurements.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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